

Effort
or
Performance

Temporal Demand
or
Frustration

Temporal Demand
or
Effort

Physical Demand
or
Frustration

Performance
or
Frustration

Physical Demand
or
Temporal Demand

Physical Demand
or
Performance

Temporal Demand
or
Mental Demand